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ISSUES OF DEVELOPING PHYSICAL CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. *This article covers the areas of physical culture of higher education students, as well as provides detailed information aimed at identifying current problems in the student's physical culture.*

Keywords: *physical education, sports facility, lifestyle, physical culture, sports results, development.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье определены направления физической культуры студентов высших образовательных учреждений, а также освещены научные взгляды к определению существующих проблем в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *физическая подготовка, спортивное сооружение, образ жизни, физическая культура, спортивные результаты, развитие.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalarining jismoniy tarbiya yo'nalishlari belgilab berilgan, shuningdek, ushbu sohadagi mavjud muammolarni aniqlash bo'yicha ilmiy qarashlar yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *jismoniy tarbiya, sport inshooti, turmush tarzi, jismoniy madaniyat, sport natijalari, rivojlanish.*

Along with improving the professional training of students of higher educational institutions, who are considered the most active members of the population and youth, the integration of physical culture and sports into their lifestyle is an urgent issue, since students of higher educational institutions are the intelligentsia, the governing and leading force of society in the future. In this regard, the role of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions is of particular importance.

Considering the requirements placed on future teachers today, it is extremely important for them to become specialists through education. After all, it is also stipulated in the relevant regulatory documents that a teacher should be progressive and exemplary in all aspects in educating the future generation. From this point of view,

the formation of a healthy lifestyle among students of pedagogical education and their improved physical culture are extremely necessary indicators. Therefore, scientific research on the physical culture of students and its development and improvement is an urgent issue. A number of scientific research works have been carried out by scientists of our republic and the CIS on a healthy lifestyle of students, their spiritual and moral education, as well as physical culture.

Of our scientists: R. Abdumalikov, I. Kushbakhtiev, A. Atoev, O. Musurmonova, O. Jamoliddinova, F. Ahmedov, R. Salomov, H. T. Rafiev. The works of F. Khojaev, Sh. Mardonov, as well as the works of scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States: M. Ya. Vilinsky, O. Yu. Milova, Ye. Yu. Andriyanova are of particular importance.

Having studied and scientifically analyzed the research works conducted by the above scientists, we set out to conduct scientific research in order to further improve the pedagogical technologies for the development of students' physical culture. For this:

Object of scientific research: analysis of the current state of pedagogical technologies aimed at developing the physical culture of students of higher educational institutions studying in the pedagogical direction;

Subject of scientific research: the foundations of the development of physical culture of students in the pedagogical direction (pedagogical technologies);

The purpose of scientific research: the development of scientific, theoretical and practical foundations for improving pedagogical technologies for developing the physical culture of students of higher educational institutions, the creation of methodological manuals and their implementation in practice were determined.

If we dwell on the tasks of scientific research, they are as follows:

scientifically determine the current state of physical culture of students; analyze the existing scientific and methodological literature on the physical culture of students and draw conclusions;

- identify the factors (indicators) that make up the physical culture of students;
- develop scientific and methodological recommendations for the development of physical culture of students;
- develop pedagogical technologies for the development of physical culture of students and implement the results of experimental testing into practice.

One of the main directions of a healthy lifestyle of students of higher educational institutions is physical culture. Indeed, it is impossible to lead a healthy lifestyle without physical culture. First of all, based on the need to clarify the concept of physical culture itself, the definitions given by specialists to this concept were studied. The concept of physical culture is defined differently by specialists. In particular, Professor

L.P. Matveev defined it as follows; “physical culture is a set of achievements in the creation and rational use of special means, methods and conditions for the purposeful implementation of physical development of members of society. Physical culture is a structural part of general culture, and its improvement is the basis for the development of society.” Based on the definitions given, indicators of students’ physical culture were determined and classified as follows:

the presence of sports facilities in a higher educational institution and their condition;

the presence of educational and regulatory documents in the field of physical education and sports of a higher educational institution and their content (curriculum, science program, work program, etc.);

the attitude of the management of a higher educational institution to creating conditions for students to engage in physical education and sports, the content of the work carried out by them (studied on the basis of a special questionnaire);

the state of methodological support for students’ physical education (textbooks, study guides, and methodological instructions);

the number of staff of specialists in the field of physical education and sports of a higher educational institution (department, teacher, trainer, other types of staff serving in the field, etc.);

the level of professional training of specialists in the field of physical education and sports in a higher educational institution (availability of scientific, degrees, titles, masters of sports and other indicators);

the level of integration of physical education and sports into the lifestyle of students (consisting of students regularly engaged in one type of sport, sports results, active student athletes, students participating in sports clubs, students regularly engaged in morning physical education, students regularly engaged in independent physical exercises, etc.);

the variety of physical education and sports events organized and held with students;

the level of health of students; physical education and sports events, classes and conditions created for them, carried out with students with disabilities. Based on the above indicators that constitute the physical culture of students, the issue of developing the physical culture of students is related not only to the pedagogical process, but also to the social, spiritual-educational, and economic spheres. In order to study the main indicators of students’ physical culture, we conducted preliminary scientific pedagogical observations. Based on this, the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute and Jizzakh State Pedagogical University were selected from higher educational institutions. About 6,500 students study at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute. There is one indoor hall, two

artificial fields, one tennis court, one badminton court, one volleyball court, one outdoor football field, and one gymnastics field for students. At the same time, these fields accommodate about 180 students. About 14,000 students study at the Jizzakh State Pedagogical University. There are two artificial fields, one football field, one basketball field, one gymnastics field, two indoor gyms, one indoor swimming pool, and running tracks for students. These sports fields accommodate about 250 students at the same time.

The presence of sports facilities is one of the main issues, of course. But the most fundamental issue is the integration of physical culture into the daily lives of students. Because even in existing sports facilities, students do not constantly engage in physical education and sports. So, the need for students to consciously and regularly engage in physical education and sports is not sufficient. There are various reasons for this, and in order to identify the existing reasons, a survey was conducted with students specifically aimed at determining the attitude (approach) of students to physical education and sports. In this regard, a survey was conducted among 200 students, including 50 II-III year students from the faculties of Russian language and literature, Uzbek language and literature, natural sciences, and preschool education of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University. Of these students, 82 were boys and 118 were girls. According to the results of the survey, the following were found:

Physical education and sports activities organized in higher education institutions were rated by 10% as unsatisfactory, 3% as good, 64% as exemplary, 23%. Among students, football - 34%, volleyball - 21%, chess and checkers - 14%, other sports - 9%, 22% reported that they do not do them at all. When asked about their independent participation in health-improving physical exercises, 18% said that they regularly do them, 46% said that they sometimes do them, and 36% said that they do not do them at all. When asked why they do not engage in physical education and sports, 26% said they do not want to, 21% said they do not consider it necessary, 33% said they do not have time, they need to study, and 20% said they want to, but the conditions are not created at the university.

In the HEMIS system, 89% said they want physical education classes to be included in the lesson schedule, 6% said they do not want to, and 5% said they do not care. If physical education classes are included, 52% said they would like them to be included once a week, and 48% said they would like them to be included twice a week. In order to further popularize physical education and sports among their students, 59% said that more physical education and sports classes should be included in the lesson schedule, and 41% said that various sports competitions should be organized.

Based on the responses received from the survey, we can see that the improvement of students' physical culture depends on many factors. As can be seen

from the data obtained from the survey, physical education and sports have not taken a full-fledged place in the daily life of students. Therefore, the majority of students do not engage in physical education and sports for various reasons. Another part of the students effectively uses the conditions created in higher educational institutions and wants them to be even better.

So, one of the main issues and a decisive indicator of improving students' physical culture is the integration of physical education and sports into their daily life.

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